

Textile Waste, Ecology and Commercialism

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ABSTRACT: The area of the fashion industry has never been stronger and the consumption and purchase of clothing, fashion, sports, children's, business is constantly growing. Parts of the world do not resist the consumer mentality, which also depends on the personal attitude of the individual, and the poorer part of the world is the one that produces clothes for minimum wages. Throughout history, clothing has served to protect against the weather, beautify and last until almost complete wear and tear. It was expensive, and the average resident didn't spend on a wardrobe like it seems today. The field of clothing is comprehensive and interesting both sociologically and psychologically and there is often an exaggeration in consumption which strengthens both production and the fall in product prices. With the fall in price, fall and quality, clothing, not fashion, because it is debatable to talk about the meaning of fashion that it had decades ago and the definition, which speeds up the process of changing the purchase and rejection of clothing. In contrast to the mass consumption of cheap clothing, there are large fashion houses with extremely unaffordable and high prices of unique items. The problem and question of ethical principles lies in piling up unnecessary clothes, buying supplies and discarding that same wardrobe in a few months. Textile waste can be recycled in organized societies, and the opposite ends up in landfills that, like any other landfill, pollute the environment. Conscientious societies or individuals will manage their clothing sensibly, but so-called "shopping" often occurs, especially among women. One of the effective ways that is slowly being accepted in all societies is second hand selling, or selling worn clothing. Until recently, it was "shameful" to buy worn clothes, while today conscious individuals buy worn clothes, finishing them, styling them and combining them into wearable variants for all time. The ethical problem that arises with this issue is the relationship between surplus and deficit and individual communities, families, countries. The problem is wastefulness and uncontrolled spending, while underdeveloped countries exploit textile workers for inhumanely low wage prices. In many countries, children's rights are also violated, where children sit connected to sewing machines throughout the day. This endangers the child's right to education, freedom, and development in the personal, intellectual, and all other fields. We observe opposites and poles from extra consumer societies or individuals who buy uncontrollably and thus support such a form of production, creating non-degradable waste, to the exploitation of the poor and children on the other hand. The gap and differences are growing, the price of labor is falling, thus the prices of products, waste and surplus are growing and the circle is closed. The poor, the ignorant sink deeper and deeper, while the excess of money and the need for imaginary desires in another part of the world grow. The same problem occurs in many other industries. The solution is very simple, but utopias are not possible until human consciousness changes, and it takes time. Technology and science are still ahead of the development of the consciousness of the majority of the population.

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Introduction

The causes of decorating and dressing the human body are different – from the mere need to protect the body from weather disasters The fashion industry clearly manifests all the main features of capitalism – the urge for-profit and consequent exploitation, the power arising from the possession of social means of production and the very real need to overthrow the precarious system in which we currently live. Today, the model of the socially acceptable identity of the individual relies mainly on the values of a capitalist society: power, money, brands and consumption, but also its short-termism. The monopolized nature of fashion media has a strong

influence on the culture of fashion and the creation of fashion laws; from fashion magazines to fashion blogs that lack critical reporting on the fashion industry today we meet on a daily basis.

Dress and fashion trends

Fashion (lat. *modus*, way of life, assembly of customs, culture of a people and group) is not a habit in dressing., " Fashion as a phenomenon of modern society means little more than the act of dressing. to an internal desire to express and emphasize diversity.

Fashion differs from the custom of dressing and decorating as a set of institutionalized norms in that it derives from modern body design as a dynamic principle of the adoption of the cult of the new. As long as there is no cult of the new, dress is conditioned by tradition, but has not yet arrived in the form, system or order of fashion. Clothing is defined by economic conditions – a form of weather endurance, and seasonal renewal. By contrast, the fundamental feature of fashion is the social dynamics of "in" and "out". In this way, it confirms the presence and permits of local and global self-determination The entire global sphere regulates and organizes hybrid identities, flexible hierarchies and a large number of mutual relationships. Clothing depends on the design process, while fashion depends on acceptance within society.

The word "fashionable" is often used incorrectly today, as a synonym for "fashion" t.j. in accordance with fashion". Terminology suggests that fashion changes every year, but changes actually occur in clothing. This does not necessarily include a change in fashion. Change is not the primary aspect of fashion – it appears in the economic concept and establishes discontinuity as the basis of continuity. Unlike dress, fashion is primarily defined by the character of social legality, not by the character of instability.

The first steps towards fashion begin when the wear is presented to a wider audience through fashion shows, photos and advertising. In doing so, actual attilements are confronted by the art of stage. Fashion gives social purpose. Fashion-assisted clothing is supplemented by social, economic, cultural and symbolic factors, which within society give additional value to the clothing item, i.e. the wearer. Fashion is so much more than just the public. Fashion is function and meaning. Fashion is created and expanded using a mimicry related to imitation, especially leading "celebrity" personalities/icons – and their odysies, as well as a mimicry of advertising images and fashion magazines. As a result of imitation, fashion – accepted by a group in society – will always be a more or less uniform image.

Fashion and consumer society

An industrial society that has transformed into a post-industrial or mass-consumption society has led to an accelerated pace of economics and industry. Fashion can no longer be as expensive as in earlier times, when the cost of first purchases or efforts to change behavior and tastes compensated the length of fashion.

The more an item is subject to a rapid change of fashion, the stronger the need for cheap products of its kind. This is where the distinctive circuit emerges: the faster fashion changes, the cheaper things become, and the cheaper they become, the faster fashion changes happen, which encourage consumers and force manufacturers.

The growing role played by broad masses of consumers in fashion trends is just a sign of greater democratisation. In reality, the imposition of fashion trends by industrialists and traders continues to prevail, because the production of goods and their distribution is in their hands, not the numerous consumer audiences.

We can understand the approach to the study of consumer culture through which we can also understand fashion and its related concepts Consumption, given the increasing

production of goods in capitalism: consumption is equivalent to the requirements of the economy.

The ways people use good to create social connections and differences.

Emotional pleasure in consumption, for dreams and desires associated with the world of goods. Modern society constantly encourages people to spend, and to exceed their needs. This creates artificial, unnecessary needs or a "demand for luxury" (which is often never met).

People are persuaded to spend more than they really need, and this is the cause of many troubles in modern society. An example of wastefulness is fashion itself, and as such it boosts sales and accelerates capital spin.

We can empirically determine the consumer society through different landmarks – improving living standards, abundance of goods and services, culture of things and leisure time, hedonistic and materialistic morality.

A society focused on spreading needs, overhauling production and mass consumption according to the rule of obsolescence, attractiveness and diversity, and leading the economy into the realm of fashion. All industries strive to mimic the methods of fashion designers. Everywhere, the scale of accelerated model change and stylization is imposed."

The form of fashion is manifested in its radicality in the accelerated pace of product change and in the volatility of industrial matters. Economic logic has simply thrown out any ideal of durability, and production and consumption are governed by the rule of ephemera.

Exploitation of workers

Fashion brands make money from exploitation. Many textile workers in the EU cannot survive on pay. Fashion brands frequently violate labor laws in Eastern European countries.

Adidas, Primark and Zara are among many Western brands accused of profiting on wages and violating workers' rights in Eastern Europe and Turkey.

About 3 million workers in countries from Slovakia to Georgia are cheap labor for Western European fashion brands, according to the report. Among the companies profiting from such practices are some luxury brands such as Prada and Hugo Boss.

In the textile industry, a predominantly female workforce is working, which is forced to work overtime, and give up annual leave in order to receive a basic salary, which is below the existential minimum.

Bulgaria and Romania are members of the EU and salaries 130 euros. Wages are also devastatingly low, and working conditions are terrible. The situation is alarming in Turkey, India and Cambodia. In all four countries, wages are far below the amount required for a dignified life, and the biggest gap exists in Bulgaria where workers receive only 10 percent of the estimated decent wage.

Workers face great stress, pressures to work faster and verbal violence by superiors, such as insulting and calling workers non-workers, slackers and similar derogatory names.

Change won't happen if we shop more "quality" than when we collectively organize and fight for them. The textilian industry in Ethiopia harvests the fruits of cheap electricity and low labor costs, as a simple seamstress earns about seven and a half kuna a day. Managers there point out that there are also opportunities for progress. One of the solutions of the textile industry would be if profits were evenly distributed to the workers who create it - fashion houses and fashion designers who encourage production. It is necessary to protect employees and only a happy employee can create and produce well and successfully.

The following standards amongst others apply to textiles: CPSIA, e.g. Standard for the Flammability of Clothing Textiles, ASTM Textile Standards, REACH Regulations for Textiles, China Product Standard for Textiles.

Instant fashion

Materialism (according to material), the philosophical view that matter is the basis of overall reality, while opinion and consciousness are its products as well as forms of its appearance; an opinion, life attitude or attitude that puts interest in material goods at the center of human impulses. People feel they should "have" and that they always "deserve better."

Greater prioritization of materialistic values, with a negative association with personal well-being, leads to more frequent feelings of negative emotions (fear, anger, sadness) and less frequent positive feelings (happiness, joy, vitality). A higher degree of materialism is associated with shorter and more conflicting interpersonal relationships, lower levels of empathy, a higher tendency to compete, a higher degree of machiavellism, a higher degree of prejudice and a greater need for social dominance, environmentally unconscious attitudes, etc. Materialistic values are not only associated with negative effects on their own well-being, but are disastrous for the environment of the individual.

Materialists and individuals with external life goals (money, fame, image) will be less involved in recycling, turning off the lights, using both sides of paper, cycling and will generally have a larger environmental footprint. Public policy is required to consider devising interventions that will make citizens more focused on internal (community aid, self-development and connection with others) and transcendental life goals to foster environmentally conscious civic behavior.

The textile business has a brutal, global competition in which every coin counts. The phenomenon of "instant fashion" resulted in t-shirts and pants being produced as quickly and cheaply as possible. Clothing has become a single-use product, as evidenced by some research data. In Germany, they came up with the data that people buy on average five new garments a month, but they wear them half as much as they did 15 years ago. Such cheap and mass-produced goods can hardly be socially and environmentally sustainable.

Modern society is based on materialism and thus encourages excessive accumulation of things and creates consumption addicts, which most people find difficult to resist because "have" becomes "be", "I buy, therefore I am". Shopping is among 10 modern addictions, reaching 5% of the population in some Western countries. How serious the problem is, the facts about emotionally and financially devastated families speak.

The growth of materialistic values undermines the human sense of well-being and as such is bad, the question is what can or should be done.

Recycling economy

Pollution is one of the biggest problems of today and has not been taken away in any area. This very problem is one of the greatest flaws of man-marking the time in which we live. Waste is not garbage, but only unused discarded waste becomes garbage. Waste is all materials resulting from human activity and are not reusable or rejected by someone. It occurs in all spheres of human activity from everyday household life to waste from service and manufacturing activities. 3 to human health and the environment. Solving this problem is a difficult task that penetrates various branches of knowledge and skills, which significantly complicates the path to efficiency. In order to establish an efficient and well-functioning waste management system, it is important that the public understands and supports the system.

The second half of the 20th century brings a significant increase in the population, especially in large cities. The rapid development of technologies and a modern way of life are creating a growing consumer society. Large amounts of waste are generated, which is a growing problem.

An economy based on the organizational structure of textile waste management is a closed circle of economics as the opposite concept of a linear economy guided by the principle of "take, make, consume and cast."

The main problem in waste management – problems based on linear management principles where the product is completely disposed of. As waste management becomes a major problem of today, linear principles are tried to be replaced with circular ones, where the object is tried to repair, dispose of or completely amended to be reused after use. This method of waste management is not only a form of waste collection, but a much more complex concept that seeks to process different developments.

The circular economy has the potential to have a positive impact on the development of today's society and it is therefore important to practice as much as possible in order to preserve the environment. Sustainability in the form of the exploitation of waste textiles would significantly reduce the re-production of fibres, textiles or clothing whose production literally destroys the environment and people's lives. In this way, management would significantly reduce the many problems of the entire fashion industry – from fiber manufacturers through large fashion corporations to every separate household.

Knowledge of the circular economy reinforces the need for the individual to treat at least his own textile waste that arises when sewing or in the form of discarded textiles and clothing, which in this day and age more and more appear all around us in the form of garbage and polluting the environment with its hoarding.

The success of individual recycling schemes depends almost entirely on customer support, i.e. the success of the Households. Laws and economic incentives can change human behaviour, but creating public awareness and the will to follow waste management instructions can also be very effective

The idea behind the revolutionary concept of 21st-century economics, i.e. the concept of economics, is that it's not the first time that the world has been in the eulau. the concept of a circular (circular) economy, is very simple but also very ambitious transition from a linear, unsustainable 'take-make-consume-cast' model in which the product reaches the end of its life cycle, to the circular model of 'take-fix-repair-recycle-recycle-reuse' Thus it will extend the life of the product and thus create new business models and new jobs with new profits but also environmental preservation.

All stages of the circular economy are interconnected, and the production and processing phase of the product is based on the concept of exchange of by-products in such a way that one waste material from one production process enters as a resource into another. The end of the cycle indicates the stages of collection and recycling, with the main aim being to reduce the amount of resources coming out of the system and ending up as waste. Such a concept lays the groundwork for eco design and eco innovation, advanced technologies, energy efficiency and the use of renewable energy sources.

The circular economy includes industry, business models and lifestyle habits that treat waste as a reuse resource. Such a challenge presents a great opportunity for the development of both SMEs, which can drive the whole economy and provide a sustainable way out of economic crises.

Circular economy in the textile sector

Today, the textile industry is one of the big environmental pollutants and large quantities of textile waste are produced every year in the municipal economy. Although it is classified as biodegradable, such classification is only partially justified as much of textile waste is poorly degradable. Incineration creates hazardous gases for the environment and the use of such technology is only possible in sufficiently large waste incineration plants equipped with efficient flue gas cleaning devices. For this reason, it is recommended to use different

recycling procedures for textile waste. In order to address textile waste, a number of initiatives are being developed around the world within the textile industry sector aimed at reducing the negative impact on the environment and the community. One such measure is the use of textiles. The average life span of garments is thought to be around three years and is then thrown away. One million tonnes of textiles are dumped in landfills each year, most of which come from households. Although most come from households, textile waste also occurs in the processes of factory production of fiber, clothing production and in the sales industry. We call such waste post-industrial waste, which is contrary to post-consumer waste, which mainly ends up at various flea markets and in charity shops.

Recycling

Recycling of textile waste is the most favorable option from an environmental and economic point of view. Recycling maintains its meaning only in the event that consumers of manufactured recycled material are insured. If there are no potential consumers, they remain a useless product – so-called, waste. If recycling is not possible, it is envisaged to burn textile waste, where the meaning is not attached to destroying textile waste but its hot use.

The recycling of textile wastes can be used for several different technological procedures. The procedures depend on the type of waste and the potential use of the resulting recycling, and it is interesting information that 97% of textile waste can be recycled. All stages of reconstruction into a new product at the same time enable the preservation of the environment and non-renewable natural resources. Textile waste recycling, in addition to economic, has an ecological component, and as a result, it has become more and more current in recent decades. Since waste material is used, it should not be a problem but a favorable opportunity. What is extremely important for this kind of narrative of management is to inform society about the possibilities and benefits of handing over unnecessary clothing and textiles. Society needs to be able to understand the organization of the collection system and its importance – which has become more frequent lately. The expansion of collection points is essential for the collection system of second-hand clothing, and in recent times they have started to appear more and more in the form of public containers for textile waste. Textiles of good quality and without errors or mechanical damage should be sorted and then passed on to the social services of local authorities and NGOs that provide clothing to those in need. Good quality clothing should also be delivered to second-hand clothing stores for charity. In addition, to prove that such clothes can be a fashion item, it is forwarded into the hands of designers who will redesign it.

Recycling is the most likely

It is feasible from absolutely all discarded materials, separating them and using separately or a combination of several different materials in one work. It can be developed in space in the form of various ideas and installations or as a surface product that can have a visual artistic purpose or subsequently be used for the performance of new usable or artistic objects. In art, the author is the one who sets boundaries and determines the final product of his performance.

Conclusions

Fashion has existed forever, and a special proliferation is experienced by the accumulation of excess value, i.e. Luxury. Until recently, it was considered class fashion, separating more layers from the lower ones (and vice versa), and serving as a means of connecting individuals of the same position. In modern society, class boundaries are softened, fashion is democratized, with fashion styles beginning to dictate wide masses, street fashion. With the development of industry, consumer society, marketing, fashion enters all layers of society, constantly accelerating the pace

of fashion changes. This has led to the fact that there is no longer one fashion, but there are only fashions, which coincides with the rise of individualization: the individual settles into society by consciously building his own lifestyle and image of life, managing the impression of himself, using fashion as a cultural code of communication and giving his personal stamp to the age of reflexive modernization. The connection between fashion and media exists on multiple levels. Fashion is simply socially relevant to be talked about in the modern media. Fashion shows from major fashion cities are featured in the daily news, and other major fashion events and fashion spectacles are being followed. Fashion magazines analyze celebrity styles, offering their readers tips on how to resolute them. Designers need celebrities as much as celebrities need designers, and the media needs both designers and celebrities to promote their products – clothing designers, and celebrities themselves. What is important for the fashion of today is its rapid expansion and change that the media allows for itself; from television, fashion magazines to fashion blogs. The theory of fashion must therefore be multidisciplinary taking into account all the breadth and depth of the fashion phenomenon in society.

The consequences of fashion popularity are the increase in production, the shorter shelf life of a particular textile product, and the exploitation of workers of the textile industry.

A large amount of textiles on the market creates more competition, falling product prices, and thus a decrease in the value of work for the textile industry. The accumulation of clothing and textile and fashion products encourages further production - as needs are dictated by consumers. A large amount of unsoated garments are produced and thus textile waste is still one of the largest pollutants of the environment. Refreshing the commoners and society is hard work, not to say utopia. It is possible to introduce legislation in relation to households towards textile waste suitable for recycling.

Textile waste, fashion and the closed circle of the economy can solve the ongoing phenomenon of increased demand and consumption of textile goods, and the distribution of profits can solve the problem of exploitation and currently too low incomes of workers in textile production.

Selective References

- Buljan, R. 1986. *Marketing i Reciklaža: Road and assistance of industrial waste*, "Zagreb" working year for the address selku, Samobor.
- Cirkularni model ekonomije, Dobrović, S. (lipanj 7.2018). *Undiscovered values of circular waste management*. <http://biramdobro.blogspot.com/2018/06/neootrkivene-vrijednostikruznog.html>, pristup 07.09. 2019.
- Dobrović, S. (lipanj 7. 2018). *Undiscovered values of circular wastemanagement*. <http://biramdobro.blogspot.com/2018/06/neootrkivene-vrijednostikruznog.html>, pristup 07.09.2020.
- Ellen MacArthur Foundation: Mission, <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/circular-economy/concept>, pristup 10.09. 20120.
- Ferenčina Bilić, Ana and Simončić, Katarina Nina. 2012. "When clothes become fashion." *TEDI: International Interdisciplinary Journal* 2: 4-7.
- Horrocks, R. 1996. *Recycling Textile and Plastic Waste*. Cambridge, England: Woodhead Publishing Limited.
- Hoskin, E. Tansy. 2015. *Stitched up to the pain. "Fashion media"*. Sandorf&Mizantrop i CIMO. Zagreb.
- Jordeva, S., Tomovska, E., Trajković, D., Zafirova, K. 2014. Textile waste as a material for thermal insulation, *Tekstil*, 63 (2014): 168-173.
- Kalambura, S i Racs, Z. 2015. *Sustainable Waste Management, Polytechnic of Health, Zagreb*, 68.
- Koszevska, M. 2018. *Circular Economy - Challenges for the Textile and Clothing Industry*, Lodz University of Technology, Autex, 18 (2018) 337-347.
- Krzyk, M., Panjan J., Drev, D. 2014. "Textile waste recycling procedures." *Tekstil* 63 (2014): 306-313.
- Loschek, Ingrid. 2009. *When clothes become fashion. "When is fashion?"* Berg. UK.
- Odak, Iva. 2003. "Fashion in society: modern sociological interpretations." *Sociology Review* 1: 97-107.
- Paić, Žarko. 2007. *Dizziness in fashion*. Altagama. Zagreb.
- Pavić, Tea. 2015. *Media influence on the creation of fashion trends*. Završni rad. Filozofski fakultet Sveučilišta u Rijeci. Rijeka. 40.str.
- Regeneracija: Misija i vizija, URL: <https://www.regeneracija.hr/index.php/hr/onamaregeneracija-hr/misija-i-vizija-regeneracija>, 08.09 2020.

- Škrlec, D. 2015. *Circular economy is the solution to the problem of rising unemployment*, <https://www.davor-skrlec.eu/cirkularna-ekonomija-predstavlja-rjesenje-problema-rastuce-nezaposlenosti/>, pristup 09.09. 20220.
- Svensen, Lars Fr. H. 2010. *Moda*. TIM press. Zagreb.
- Wang, Y. 2006. *Recycling in Textiles*. The Textile Institute, Cambridge, England: Woodhead Publishing Limited.
- Zgrabljic Rotar, Nada. 2005. "*Media literacy and civil society*." MediaCentar. Sarajevo.